

after sowing (DAS) and 25% N at 40 DAS.

Data on average depth of seed placement, seed distribution efficiency (SDE), plant population/ m-row length,

energy use efficiency (EUE), and comparative performance index (CPI = product of energy, SDE, and grain yield factors) are in Table 2. The two-row implement factory seed-cum-fertilizer

drill had the highest CPI (3.33), SDE (81%), and number of plants/m-row (28). The three-row drill appeared to have had higher friction in the metering device. □

Environmental analysis

Effect of season on rice response, production efficiency, and recovery of applied N

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We studied the response, production efficiency, and recovery of applied N in rice, with and without soil-applied granular insecticides during the southwest monsoon (Jun-Sep 1982), northeast monsoon (Sep-Dec 1982), summer (Jan-Apr 1983), and southwest monsoon (Jan-Sep 1983).

Soil was clay loam, pH 8.2, with 1% organic matter, 196-9.5-200 ppm available NPK, 598 ppm total soil N, and 0.4 ppm DTPH extractable Zn. The experiments were factorial combinations

of 4 levels of N (0, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha) and 3 levels of insecticides (no insecticide, carbofuran 3% granular at 0.75 kg ai/ha, and phorate 10% granules at 1.0 kg ai/ha) in a randomized block design with 6 replications.

Rice response to N (kg grain produced: kg of N applied) and N recovery were highest when N was applied with carbofuran or phorate (see table).

Across the seasons, response and N recovery were higher in summer; production efficiency was higher in the northeast monsoon season. □

Response, production efficiency, and recovery of N applied with and without insecticide, by season.^a Coimbatore, India, 1982-83.

	SWM 1982	NEM 1982	SUM 1983	SWM 1983
<i>Response (kg grain:kg N)</i>				
N alone	12	12	16	21
N + carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha	19	20	25	22
N + phorate at 1.0 kg ai/ha	20	21	26	25
<i>Production efficiency (kg grain:kg N)</i>				
N alone	39	70	45	56
N + carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha	34	12	41	56
N + phorate at 1.0 kg ai/ha	38	23	44	66
<i>N recovery (%)</i>				
N alone	28	17	38	34
N + carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha	55	29	62	39
N + phorate at 1.0 kg ai/ha	53	29	58	34

^aSWM = southwest monsoon, NEM = northeast monsoon, SUM = summer.

Farming systems

Growth and yield of wet season rice with tilapia fish

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We studied growth and yield of rice and fish in the Cropping Systems Research site at Memari in 1987 (Jun-Dec) wet season. The experiment consisted of a plot of rice without fish and one of rice with tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*).

Soil was clay loam with pH 6.5 - 7.0.

Plots were thoroughly plowed and 9 t farmyard manure/ha incorporated. Plots were 20 × 38 m with a shallow 75- × 50-cm perimeter canal and a trapezoidal protective dike bounding the canal. To encourage better fish movement, 2 central drains, each 50 cm wide and 30 cm deep, were dug lengthwise across the plot of rice with fish.

Pankaj, a recommended photoperiod-sensitive lowland rice variety, was transplanted, 2 seedlings at 15- × 20-cm spacing/hill, in early Aug, with 100 kg N/ha applied 1/2 at land preparation and 1/2 in equal splits 1 mo after transplanting and 1 wk before flowering; 18 kg P and 33 kg K/ha were added at land preparation. Pump water was used

Growth and yield of rice + fish at Bardhaman, West Bengal, 1987 wet season.

Characteristic	Rice without fish	Rice + fish
<i>Rice</i>		
Plant height (cm)	133.2	120.8
Effective tillers/plant	12.0	15.2
Panicle length (cm)	26.4	26.8
Grains/panicle	158.2	178.4
Grain yield (t/ha)	4.1	4.9
Straw yield (t/ha)	5.2	6.0
<i>Fish</i>		
Recovery (%)	—	81.3
Increase in length (cm)	—	8.2
Increase in weight (g)	—	96.4
Fish yield (t/ha)	—	0.7

to irrigate as needed. Water depth, 3-5 cm at the outset, was gradually increased to 10-12 cm.